

Analysis of Member States' 2025 GHG projections Submitted under Art 38 (1)(b) of the Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999

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Executive summary

From March 15, 2021 onwards, and every two years thereafter, EU Member States have to report their **GHG projections** in accordance with Art. 18.1(b) of the Regulation Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999 (Gov. Reg.) and the related Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1208 and its amendment, Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/1281, which repealed the EU Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (MMR) (EU no. 525/2012).

The year **2025 represented a mandatory reporting year** under the Governance Regulation. All Member States were therefore required to submit their updated GHG projections through the Reportnet 3.0 platform, using the reporting templates defined under the Implementing Regulation. The European Topic Centre on Climate change Mitigation (ETC CM) supports the European Environment Agency (EEA) in the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of these submissions and in the preparation of the consolidated EU greenhouse gas (GHG) projections dataset.

This report presents the **main findings from the QA/QC process** carried out by the ETC CM for the 2025 GHG projections mandatory reporting cycle in accordance with Article 18(1)(b) of the Governance Regulation (EU) 2018/1999. The QA/QC procedure covered all GHG projections submissions provided through the Reportnet 3.0 platform by EU Member States, including the relevant submissions from the European Economic Area (EEA)/ European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Iceland, Norway and Switzerland.

At the time of writing this report, a **total of 25 EU Member States and three EEA/EFTA countries submitted GHG projections in 2025**. As such, the analysis and graphs in this report are based on the 25 EU Member State submissions received. During the QA/QC process, Belgium and Romania did not submit updated projections, and their datasets were gap-filled by the ETC CM in coordination with the Member States and the European Environment Agency (EEA). For Belgium, the 2024 submission was used as the most recent available data and extrapolated up to 2055. For Romania, GHG projections were constructed by the ETC CM using the latest GHG inventory (2025 submission, reference year 2023) and the growth rates from the decarbonisation pathways used for the Final updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) reported by Romania under the Governance Regulation. Further details on both cases are provided in Box 2.1.

The **number of findings** shared on average per reporting country was 22, higher than during the 2023 mandatory reporting cycle, with most of the findings being solved directly with Member States' experts in the communication process. The largest share of the findings concerned multiple sectors simultaneously.

Like in previous mandatory reporting years, a posing challenge was the **timeliness** of the submissions of the Member States. Only 12 Member States submitted their GHG projections on or before the official deadline of 15 March 2025, compared to 15 in 2023, while another seven Member States submitted within six weeks of the deadline. The last initial submission of the 25 Member States was received in early June 2025. In total, 18 Member States provided at least one resubmission (compared with 16 in 2023); six submitted a second resubmission, and two submitted a third one. On average, the interval between first and final submission amounted to around 81 days, compared to 54 days in 2023. The latest resubmission was received as late as 27 August 2025.

The **completeness** of submissions remained high for mandatory elements, with 25 Member States providing updated GHG projections as required under Article 18(1)(b). All Member States submitted the With Existing Measures (WEM) scenario with full sector and gas coverage and included Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) projections. Voluntary elements saw a slight improvement compared

to 2023, with 21 Member States submitting a With Additional Measures (WAM) scenarios and five providing a Without Measures (WOM) projections.

Most Member States selected either 2022 or 2023 as their **reference year**, showing convergence around recent inventory submissions as the base dataset. Only a few Member States opted for earlier years, such as 2019, 2020 and 2021. Intermediate years were reported voluntarily by 16 Member States up to 2040 and 13 Member States up to 2050 and, where missing, data were gap-filled by the ETC CM.

Time series consistency improved through targeted checks, ensuring Member States did not include historical values without projections and that interpolation or extrapolation maintained smooth trends across the EU aggregate.

To ensure the **consistency and comparability** of the scenarios, the ETC CM compares the results of the WEM, WAM and WOM scenarios. 18 Member States showed higher WAM than WEM projections for at least one sector or gas, prompting clarification requests and recommendations to document these cases in technical reports. Unit consistency slightly deteriorated compared to 2023, but all issues were corrected or clarified through QA/QC.

Regarding the **accuracy and transparency** of the reported trends, the ETC CM sought for clarification when outliers, implausible trends or significant recalculations were identified, but without any further explanation in the written report. The sum checks identified issues in six Member States, primarily due to manual errors that were subsequently corrected through resubmission or adjustments by the ETC CM. Trend and outlier checks resulted in 25 questions across 14 Member States, most of which were clarified by Member States through additional reporting or explanations. Recalculation checks led to 21 questions, mainly related to methodological updates or new data inputs, requiring no corrective action by the ETC CM.

The number of reported **parameters** increased substantially in 2025. Population, gross domestic product (GDP), and European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) price were among the most reported parameters, while more specialised variables were used for energy, Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use (AFOLU), and industrial projections. The Netherlands remained the only Member State to explicitly report parameters related to CO₂ capture from bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and fossil sources (new reporting element).

Finally, the 2025 reporting cycle introduced **new reporting elements** aimed at improving transparency and completeness. These include the mandatory reporting of projected values of CO₂ capture for permanent storage based on the source of emissions if negative emissions have been incorporated into the category values in Table 1a (biogenic CO₂ capture (e.g. BECCS) vs fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture) and two additional LULUCF sub-categories – 4.I Atmospheric deposition and 4.J Nitrogen leaching and run-off. Reporting coverage for these new elements varied, with Spain and Sweden emerging as frontrunners in the detailed reporting of the new LULUCF categories.

Despite the challenges faced during the 2025 cycle, countries are successfully progressing toward enhanced reporting under the Government Regulation. Similarly to previous mandatory reporting cycles, the **main challenge** for future mandatory and non-mandatory reporting cycles is the timeliness of reporting by Member States, with delayed (re)submissions negatively influencing the QA/QC process and the related products and outcomes.

1 Introduction

From March 15, 2021 onwards, and every two years thereafter, EU Member States have to report their greenhouse gas (GHG) projections in accordance with Art. 18.1(b) of the Regulation Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999 (Gov. Reg.) and the related Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1208 and its amendment, Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/1281, which repealed the EU Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (MMR) (EU no. 525/2012).

The year 2025 represented a mandatory reporting year under the Governance Regulation. All Member States were therefore required to submit their updated GHG projections through the Reportnet 3.0 platform, using the reporting templates defined under the Implementing Regulation. The European Topic Centre on Climate change Mitigation (ETC CM) supports the European Environment Agency (EEA) in the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of these submissions and in the preparation of the consolidated EU GHG projections dataset. Reportnet 3.0 is a data collection and reporting system managed by the EEA. It supports the collection, validation and submission of information from Member States, including data on policies and measures (PaMs), projections and related parameters, in line with the EU Governance Regulation reporting requirements.

New updated reporting templates and elements have been introduced in 2025 (see Box 1.1.). Additional information and guidance documents for Member States covering changes introduced by the new Gov. Reg. and Reportnet 3.0 platform can be found here: [Gov.Reg. Projections — Eionet Portal \(europa.eu\)](#).

Box 1.1 Summary of main changes in reporting under the Governance Regulation

- Inclusion of new updates in reporting templates:
 - Projection horizon extended to 2055.
 - Monetary reference value updated to EUR (2023).
 - Addition of two new sub-categories in Table 1a related to LULUCF:
 - 4.I Atmospheric deposition
 - 4.J Nitrogen leaching and run-off
 - In Table 5b, the year bracket 2026–2030 has been divided into 2026–2029 and 2030. The columns 2026–2029 and 2030 are shaded, as they are not to be filled in (except for Effort Sharing sectors and Total).
 - A Total row has been added at the bottom to allow reporting of aggregated values.
 - In Table 3, section 5 (Other parameters and variables), projected values of total CO₂ capture must be reported according to the source of emissions (biogenic vs. fossil fuel), if negative emissions are incorporated in Table 1a category values.
- Outdated references and text from previous (voluntary) reporting years have been removed.
- Minor editorial improvements throughout the text.

1.1 The Union System for projections

The Union system for PaMs and for projections (Figure 1.1) represents the institutional, legal, and procedural arrangements established for reporting on PaMs and projections of anthropogenic emissions by sources and removals by sinks of GHG not controlled by the Montreal Protocol. At the moment of writing this report, the [document detailing the elements](#) of the Union system has not been updated to reflect the transition from the MMR to the Governance Regulation.

Overall responsibility for the Union system for PaMs and projections of anthropogenic GHG emissions by sources and removals by sinks rests with the European Commission, more specifically its Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA). The outcome of the system provides data for the evaluation of progress towards EU and international commitments, as per Article 39 of the Governance Regulation and 4 and 12 of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and 3 of the Kyoto Protocol.

In accordance with point (a) of Article 44(1) of the Governance Regulation (EU/2018/1999), the Climate Change Committee established under Article 3 of Regulation (EU) No 182/2011 assists the Commission. The Committee is composed of representatives of the Member States and chaired by a representative of the Commission.

Working Group 2 'Implementation of the Effort Sharing Decision, Policies and Measures and Projections' was established under the Climate Change Committee as a regular body for exchange of information on projections and PaMs between the Commission, the EEA, and the Member States (European Commission, 2015).

Figure 1.1 Union System for Policies and Measures and Projections

The Union's system for policies and measures and projections

Source: Adapted from European Commission, 2015.

1.2 Reporting requirements

Article 18 (1) (b) of the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 (Gov. Reg.) and Article 38 of the related Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1208 and its amendment, Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/1281, set out the details for Member States to provide information on national GHG projections. Every two years (starting from 2021 with the new reporting under the Gov. Reg.), the Member States shall report GHG projections and accompanying information to the European Union (EU). In total, there are seven reporting tables for the reporting of GHG projections and the related information under the Gov. Reg. which are briefly summarised in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2 Overview of reporting tables for GHG projections and related information in accordance with Article 18 (1) (b) of the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 (Gov. Reg.) and Article 38 of the related Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1208 and its amendment, Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/1281.

The main mandatory elements of this reporting obligation are:

- GHG projections reported by gas (Total GHGs, Total ETS GHGs, Total ESR GHGs, CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, HFC, PFC, SF₆, NF₃, unspecified mix of HFCs and PFCs)
- the reference year, 2020, 2025, 2030, and 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050, and 2055
- Inventory version to which the GHG projections are related
- Split by sectors and categories in line with the common reporting format (CRF) format
- Detailed Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) projections including projections assigned to the LULUCF accounting categories according to the Governance Regulation (EU) 2018/841 and Implementation Regulation (EU) 2020/1208
- Sectoral split into ETS and ESR emissions
- A 'with existing measures' scenario (WEM)
- Information on models
- Provision of a sensitivity analysis of the total GHG, ETS and ESR
- Underlying key parameters for the sensitivity analysis
- Provision of a description of methodologies, models, and underlying assumptions
- Provision of parameters and variables used in the projections

1.3 Scope of the QA/QC

The European Commission (DG CLIMA) is responsible for coordinating QA/QC activities on GHG projections at EU level and to ensure that the objectives of the QA/QC programme are fulfilled. The EEA is responsible for the annual implementation of the QA/QC procedures and is assisted by the ETC CM.

The Union projections are compiled as the sum of all EU Member States projections, therefore it is very important that the Member States data meet certain quality objectives. The data quality objectives pursued by this QA/QC procedure are based on the core principles of data quality: transparency, completeness, consistency, comparability, and accuracy. These quality principles have been initially defined by the IPCC to characterise the quality of historical emission inventories. They have a slightly different scope in the context of emission projections.

Transparency: means to ensure that transparent information is provided on underlying assumptions, methodologies used, and sensitivity analysis performed in Member States' national projections to enable further assessment by users of the reported information and for the purpose of the compilation of Union GHG projections.

Completeness: means to ensure that projections are reported by Member States for all years, gases, sources and sinks as required under the Gov. Reg., so that projections are available for the entire EU area to enable further assessment by users of the reported information and for the purpose of the Union GHG projections compilation (see also reporting requirements in chapter 2.2).

Consistency: means to ensure internal time series consistency in all elements of national and Union GHG projections over a period of historic and future years as well as to ensure that key input parameters and assumptions are aligned across different sectors for national GHG projections and across different Member States for Union GHG projections (see also reporting requirements in chapter 2.3 and 2.4).

Comparability: means to ensure that national estimates of projected emissions and removals reported by Member States are comparable across Member States. The allocation of different sectors and categories by gas follows the split in accordance with the Gov. Reg. which also defines projections horizon, reference

year (starting year), ETS/ESR split, EU PaMs to be taken into account and harmonised key assumptions (see also reporting requirements in chapter 2.3).

Accuracy: means that projected estimates are accurate in the sense that they are plausible and neither systematically over- nor underestimated as far as can be judged and that uncertainties inherent to the methodology and input data are reduced as far as practicable. In addition, it should be ensured that an accurate aggregation of sectors for national GHG projections and an accurate aggregation of Member States for the Union GHG projections are provided.

An additional quality principle used in this context is **timeliness** and it means that national GHG projections are submitted by 15 March for each reporting year in accordance with the Gov. Reg. Further details on the QA/QC procedure are provided in the *ETC-CM_Report_2025_QAQC Procedure*.

With the introduction of the reporting requirements under Article 18(1)(b) of the Governance Regulation, the ETC-CM adapted and expanded its QA/QC checks to align with the updated framework. In addition to extending all checks to cover the new gases and sectors, several key modifications were incorporated:

- The completeness check is applied to all reporting tables (1a, 1b, 2, 3, 4, 5a, 5b, 6 and 7) as well as the report.
- The consistency check is extended to the LULUCF related information (provided in tables 1b and 5a).
- The sum check is extended to the LULUCF related information provided in tables 1b and 5a.
- The sensitivity analysis checks the units, parameters and scenarios related to the sensitivity scenarios (table 6, 7 and the report).
- The interlinkages check based on Gov. Reg. Annex VI (e) checks that information on interlinkages between PaMs and projections are provided.
- The time series check ensures that Member States do not report historical values for sectors/categories for which no projections are available in the reporting template because this causes strange jumps in the time series.

Additional information and guidance documents for Member States covering changes introduced by the new Gov. Reg. and Reportnet 3.0 platform can be found here: [Gov. Reg. Projections — Eionet Portal \(europa.eu\)](#)

The aggregated dataset for EU 27 does not include all emission sources as reported in the GHG projections. It includes main sectors and categories which are relevant to explain trends, and which are mandatory to report. This selection increases constantly to adapt to the design of European PaMs. Table 1.1 provides an overview of the sectors and categories included in the current EU aggregated dataset.

Table 1.1 Sector codes and sector names of the EU aggregated projections dataset

Sector code	Sector name	Sector code	Sector name
1	Energy	3	Agriculture
1.A.1	Energy industries	4	Land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF)
1.A.2	Manufacturing industries and construction	4.A	Forest land
1.A.3	Transport	4.B	Cropland
1.A.3.a	Domestic aviation	4.C	Grassland
1.A.3.b	Road transportation	4.D	Wetlands
1.A.3.c	Railways	4.E	Settlements
1.A.3.d	Domestic navigation	4.F	Other land
1.A.3.e	Other transportation	4.G	Harvested wood products
1.A.4	Other sectors	4.H	Other
1.A.4.a	Commercial/Institutional	4.I	Atmospheric deposition
1.A.4.b	Residential	4.J	Nitrogen leaching and run-off
1.A.5	Other	5	Waste
1.B	Fugitive emissions from fuels	M.IB aviation	Memo item: International bunkers aviation
1.C	CO ₂ transport and storage	M.IB navigation	Memo item: International bunkers navigation
2	Industrial processes and product use	Total excl. LULUCF	Total excluding LULUCF
2.A	Mineral industry	Total excl. LULUCF incl. Int. aviation	Total excluding LULUCF including the mem item international aviation (calculated by the ETC CM)
2.B	Chemical industry	Indirect CO₂	Indirect CO ₂ emissions
2.C	Metal industry		

2 Results from the quality checking procedure

At the time of writing this report, 25 EU Member States and three EEA/EFTA countries (Iceland, Norway and Switzerland) provided information on GHG projections as per Art. 18 (1) (b) of the Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999 (Gov. Reg.)

During the QA/QC procedure, Belgium and Romania had not submitted updated projections in 2025. Therefore, projections data for Belgium and Romania was gap-filled by the ETC CM and combined with the submissions made in 2025 by the other Member States to create the EU27 projections dataset for 2025. For Belgium, the 2024 submission was used as the most recent available data and extrapolated up to 2055. For Romania, however, the latest submission dated from 2023, requiring the ETC CM to develop GHG projections using the latest GHG inventory (2025 submission, reference year 2023) and the growth rates from the decarbonisation pathways used for the Final updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) reported by Romania under the Governance Regulation. Box 2.1 provides a detailed methodological explanation for both countries.

The EU27 dataset for 2025 includes the GHG projections for all main categories and years, starting with the EU reference year (2023) until 2055. Intermediate years were gap-filled with linear interpolation if not reported. The dataset is prepared for all gases, including the ETS/ESR split.

Box 2.1. Gap-filling procedures applied for Belgium and Romania

Belgium and Romania did not submit updated projections in 2025. In coordination with the European Commission, the EEA proceeded with gap-filling to ensure the completeness and consistency of the EU27 dataset.

Belgium

The latest available submission from Belgium (2024) was used in the EU27 dataset. As the projections horizon was extended to 2055 in 2025, Belgium's 2024 submission was extrapolated to 2055 by applying the 2050 values as constant values for the period 2051-2055.

Romania

Romania's GHG projections were developed using the latest GHG inventory (2025 submission, reference year 2023) and the growth rates from the decarbonisation pathways used for the Final updated NECP 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) reported by Romania under the Governance Regulation. The 2024 NECP represents Romania's most recent strategic and analytical framework, integrating updated post-2020 policies, measures, and targets aligned with the EU 2030 climate and energy objectives. It provides forward-looking assumptions on energy demand, renewables deployment, and decarbonisation pathways, and therefore offers a credible foundation for extrapolation.

As the NECP projections typically extend only to 2030 or 2040, the ETC CM extrapolated the resulting projections to 2055, while recognising the increased uncertainty beyond the original time horizon. In addition, since the NECP provides only total GHG projections, without full sectoral and gas detail, ESR/ETS separation or complete coverage of inventory emissions, several assumptions and additional calculations were required to construct a consistent reference dataset.

This approach leverages Romania's most up-to-date national strategies, ensuring policy relevance while maintaining technical consistency with EU-level reporting standards. It marks the first time such an approach has been applied for gap-filling Member State projections data, reflecting both the evolving national planning landscape and the ETC CM's methodological adaptability.

2.1 Communication with the Member States

2.1.1 Number of questions per Member State

Figure 2.1 displays the number of questions the ETC CM experts asked each of the Member States during the QA/QC procedure in 2025. On average, the ETC CM experts raised around 22 questions by Member State in 2025, compared to 17 in 2023. It is important to note that no questions were directed to Belgium and Romania since they did not submit updated projections during the QA/QC procedure in 2025.

In total, 548 questions were recorded in the 2025 QA/QC procedure, an increase compared to the 451 questions asked in the last mandatory reporting cycle in 2023. 94% of the questions raised by the ETC CM experts in 2025 could be directly solved with the Member States in the communication process (49.7% in 2023) and the remaining 6% of the questions were solved by the reviewers (18.9% in 2023). All issues were communicated to the Member States' experts in a dedicated communication log file.

Despite the observations made above, it should be noted that the number of questions raised to a Member State as indicated in Figure 2.1 does not necessarily constitute an ideal indicator for the quality of a submission. Indeed, in many cases, questions concerning similar issues for different categories were

grouped as a single question in the final questions count, hence altering to some degree the effective number of issues identified.

Figure 2.1 Number of questions per Member State

2.1.2 Subject of the questions

Figure 2.2 displays the number of times a specific quality check constituted the basis of a question raised by the ETC CM experts in the 2025 QA/QC procedure.

In the 2025 reporting cycle, like in the last mandatory reporting cycle in 2023, most of the questions were related to completeness (229 questions out of 548 in 2025, and 163 out of 451 in 2023). Other checks also triggered a significant number of questions, such as the consistency check (57 questions), the historic parameters check (56 questions), and the check against EC recommended parameters (47 questions). Note that in 2023 too, EC recommended parameters (43 questions) and consistency (41 questions) raised a considerable number of questions.

It can be concluded from these figures that the initial submissions provided by Member States in 2025, before the QA/QC process, were not fully complete, lacked consistency, and that parameter usage was not fully adequate. However, through the QA/QC process, Member States provided updated and / or additional information, leading to significant quality improvements in their submissions.

Figure 2.2 Number of questions per check

2.1.3 Distribution of questions across categories

Figure 2.3 displays the distribution of questions across categories or sectors in 2025. Like in the last compulsory reporting cycle, most of the questions in the 2025 QA/QC process concerned all/multiple categories (44.2% in 2025 and 39% in 2023) or were not related to any specific category (38.3% in 2025 and 38.1% in 2023) and rather concerned general issues on the submission (e.g., no model factsheet provided, reporting of indirect CO₂, etc.). This confirms the shift from category-specific to broader questions observed from 2021 onwards. Category-specific questions amounted in 2025 to shares of 4.6%, 1.3%, 1.1%, 4.9%, and 1.3% for “Energy”, “Industrial processes”, “Agriculture”, “LULUCF”, and “Waste”, respectively.

Figure 2.3 Distribution of questions across categories

Note: If a question concerned more than one sub-sector falling under the same sector (e.g. “1.A.1.” and “1.A.5.”), the question was recorded under the label of that specific sector only (here “1. Energy”). On the other hand, if a question concerned sub-sectors falling under different sectors (e.g., “4.H” and “1.A.3.”), or different categories (e.g., “Total excluding LULUCF” and “2. Industrial processes”), the question was recorded under “all/multiple sectors”. The label “all/multiple sectors” was also applied to questions which explicitly concerned all sectors. “N/A” refers to more general questions which did not relate to a specific category.

2.1.4 Responsiveness and overall collaboration

Throughout the 2025 QA/QC process, overall responsiveness and collaboration with the Member States was positive, with most Member States providing feedback and clarifications within the established deadlines. The ETC CM was therefore able to conclude most of the general QA/QC process by July 2025. This represents a significant improvement compared to the 2023 QA/QC cycle, when communications and revisions extended until September.

While the process was largely smooth, a few exceptions occurred, with additional follow-ups and clarifications required beyond July for several Member States, including Cyprus, Denmark, Malta, France, and Portugal. These cases involved delayed resubmissions, incomplete reporting in certain tables, or inconsistencies. Nevertheless, all issues were resolved through targeted bilateral communication between the ETC CM task leader and national experts.

Overall, the collaboration with Member States remained constructive and solution-oriented. The ETC CM developed and proposed tailored solutions to address country-specific challenges, which were discussed and agreed upon bilaterally to ensure the completeness and consistency of the EU27 projections dataset.

2.2 Completeness and Timeliness

2.2.1 Date of submission and resubmissions

Figure 2.4 illustrates the timeliness of submissions in the 2025 reporting cycle. Green dots indicate the dates of countries' first official submission, whereas blue, purple, and yellow dots depict dates of possible resubmissions.

In 2025, 12 Member States (Czechia, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Finland, Croatia, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia and Slovakia) first submitted their projections on or before the official deadlines of 15 March 2025, while 7 Member States submitted within 6 weeks of the deadline (Denmark, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, and Sweden). In comparison, in 2023, 15 Member States submitted before the deadline and 4 submitted within 6 weeks of it. The last country to provide its initial submission in 2025 was Cyprus at the beginning of June 2025. As previously mentioned, during the QA/QC procedure, Belgium and Romania had not submitted any data.

In total, 18 Member States provided a resubmission in 2025 (compared to 16 in 2023), out of which six resubmitted a second time (one Member State in 2023) and two (no Member State in 2023) a third time (Bulgaria, Denmark). A resubmission was not necessary for Austria, Greece, Spain, Latvia, Poland, Sweden and Slovakia since their first submission passed the quality standards.

On average, the number of days between the first and the final submission for Member States that had to resubmit one or several times in 2025 amounted to 81 days approximately, an increase compared to the average 54 days in the 2023 cycle. In 2025, Member States resubmitted their final revised datasets between April and August 2025 (in 2023, Member States had resubmitted their revised datasets between May and August 2025). The final resubmission was received from France on 27 August 2025.

Figure 2.4 Timeliness of submissions by EU Member States

2.2.2 General completeness of submissions

Table 2.1 presents the completeness of mandatory and voluntary information reported by Member States in 2025.

In the 2025 mandatory reporting cycle, 25 Member States provided updated GHG projections as per Art. 18 (1) (b) of the Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999 (i.e. all but Belgium and Romania). These 25 Member States all submitted the mandatory With Existing Measures (WEM) scenario in Table 1a, provided the required sector and gas split, LULUCF projections both accounted and detailed, parameters, and model factsheets. Furthermore, 17 Member States (Austria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Finland, France, Croatia, Ireland, Lithuania, Latvia, Malta, the Netherlands, Sweden and Slovenia) furnished information on sensitivity analysis and 18 submitted an accompanying technical report (Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Finland, Croatia, Italy, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Latvia, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, Slovenia, and Slovakia).

In 2025, a total of 21 Member States provided a With Additional Measures (WAM) scenario (all but Denmark, Estonia, Finland, and Sweden), while 5 Member States provided a Without Measures (WOM) scenario (Austria, Cyprus, Germany, Estonia, and Slovakia). In addition, 19 Member States provided indicators (Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Spain, France, Croatia, Italy, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Latvia, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, and Slovakia).

Table 2.1 Overview on completeness of reporting

	Updated projections	Required sector split	Required GHG split	Detailed LULUCF Projections	LULUCF accounted projections	Scenarios			Provision of parameters	Sensitivity analysis	Model factsheet/ description	Report	Provision of indicators
						WEM	WAM	WOM					
AT									*				
BE													
BG													
CY									*				
CZ									*				
DE									*				
DK									*				
EE									*				
EL									*				
ES									*				
FI									*				
FR									*				
HR									*				
HU									*				
IE									*				
IT									*				
LT									*				
LU									*				
LV									*				
MT									*				
NL									*				
PL									*				
PT									*				
RO									*				
SE									*				
SI									*				
SK									*				

Legend:

	Yes, reported
	Not reported (mandatory reporting items)
	Not reported but planned (mandatory reporting items)
	Not reported (voluntary reporting items)

Notes: 1) * Tables 6 and 7 reported, ** only Table 6 or Table 7 was submitted
 2) As Belgium and Romania did not submit any project in the 2025 cycle, the table shows all its mandatory and voluntary information as not reported (in red and orange).

In comparison, in the 2023 mandatory reporting cycle, full compliance was achieved on the mandatory WEM scenario in Table 1a., updated projections, the comprehensive sector and gas split for the WEM scenario in Table 1a., and LULUCF projections both accounted and detailed. Germany and Italy did not supply model fact sheets in 2023. However, all Member States submitted a specific report for projections or a combined report for projections and PaMs. Furthermore, Greece was the only Member State that did not provide its parameters.

In 2023, 19 Member States furnished information on sensitivity analysis (Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, France, Italy, Malta, Portugal, and Slovakia failed to do so). Only Cyprus, Malta, and Slovenia provided a WOM scenario, while 16 Member States provided a WAM scenario (Bulgaria, Czechia, Germany, Estonia, Spain, Finland, Croatia, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, and Slovakia). 21 Member States reported on their indicators (all but Belgium, Czechia, Greece, Finland, Ireland and Sweden).

In conclusion, neglecting the cases of Belgium and Romania for 2025, a similar level of completeness was achieved in 2025 and 2023 (except for the provision of technical reports, which was significantly lower in 2025).

2.2.3 Completeness of data

Table 2.2 summarises the completeness of the mandatory data, categorised by gas, submitted in Table 1a for the 2025 reporting cycle. The table outlines the number of countries, with a maximum of 25 (25 Member States submissions excluding Belgium and Romania), that submitted the required numerical data

or appropriate notation keys. In cases where specific gases are not applicable to certain sectors, the corresponding cells are shaded in grey.

Completeness in the reporting of numeric emissions and notation key data for all sector-gas combinations was comparable in the 2023 mandatory reporting cycle and in the 2025 cycle. Since Belgium and Romania did not provide GHG projections in 2025 during the QA/QC procedure, a maximum of 25 out of 27 Member States reported a values or notation keys for a given sector-gas category in 2025, whereas that number reached 27 out of 27 as a maximum in 2023.

Completeness across Member States in 2025 was generally strong. However, lower completeness was observed for certain categories, particularly the unspecified mix of HFCs and PFCs, as well as the newly introduced LULUCF subcategories 4.I Atmospheric Deposition and 4.J Nitrogen Leaching and Run-off. In these cases, a slight decrease in completeness was noted, with 23 out of 25 Member States reporting either numerical values or notation keys.

Table 2.2 Number of EU Member States that reported numeric emissions data or notation keys per sector and per gas under the ‘WEM’ scenario

Category	CO2	N2O	CH4	HFC	PFC	Unspecified	SF6	NF3	Total	ETS	ESR
1. Energy	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A. Fuel combustion	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A.1. Energy industries	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A.1.a. Public electricity and heat production	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A.1.b. Petroleum refining	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A.1.c. Manufacture of solid fuels and other ene	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A.2. Manufacturing industries and construction	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.3. Transport	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.A.3.a. Domestic aviation	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
1.A.3.b. Road transportation	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.3.c. Railways	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.3.d. Domestic navigation	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.3.e. Other transportation	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	23	24
1.A.4. Other sectors	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.4.a. Commercial/Institutional	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.4.b. Residential	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.4.c. Agriculture/Forestry/Fishing	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.A.5. Other	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	25
1.B. Fugitive emissions from fuels	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.B.1. Solid fuels	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	24
1.B.2. Oil and natural gas and other emissions fro	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
1.C. CO2 transport and storage	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	24	24
2. Industrial processes	25	25	25	25	25	23	25	24	25	25	25
2.A. Mineral Industry	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
2.A.1. Cement production	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
2.B. Chemical industry	25	25	25	24	24	23	24	24	25	25	25
2.C. Metal industry	25	25	25	24	24	23	24	24	25	25	25
2.C.1. Iron and steel production	25	25	25	24	24	23	24	24	25	24	24
2.D. Non-energy products from fuels and solven	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	25
2.E. Electronics industry	N/A	N/A	N/A	24	25	23	24	24	25	25	25
2.F. Product uses as substitutes for ODS (8)	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	25	23	24	24	25	25	25
2.G. Other product manufacture and use	25	25	25	24	24	23	25	24	25	25	25
2.H. Other	25	25	25	24	24	23	24	24	25	25	25
3. Agriculture	24	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.A. Enteric fermentation	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.B. Manure management	N/A	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.C. Rice cultivation	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	24
3.D. Agricultural soils	N/A	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.E. Prescribed burning of savannahs	N/A	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	24
3.F. Field burning of agricultural residues	N/A	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.G. Liming	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.H. Urea application	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.I. Other carbon-containing fertilizers	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
3.J. Other (please specify)	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	24
4. Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULU	25	N/A	24	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.A. Forest land	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.B. Cropland	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.C. Grassland	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.D. Wetlands	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.E. Settlements	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.F. Other Land	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	24	N/A	N/A
4.G. Harvested wood products	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
4.H. Other	25	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	24	N/A	N/A
4.I. Atmospheric deposition	23	N/A	22	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	22	N/A	N/A
4.J. Nitrogen leaching and run-off	23	N/A	22	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	22	N/A	N/A
5. Waste	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
5.A. Solid Waste Disposal	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
5.B. Biological treatment of solid waste	N/A	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
5.C. Incineration and open burning of waste	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
5.D. Wastewater treatment and discharge	N/A	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
5.E. Other (please specify)	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	25
CO2 captured	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	24	N/A	N/A
CO2 emissions from biomass	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	24	N/A	N/A
International bunkers	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
IB.Aviation	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
IB.Navigation	24	24	24	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	23	N/A	N/A
Indirect CO2 (if available) (10)	25	25	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25	N/A	N/A
Total excluding LULUCF	25	25	25	25	25	23	25	24	25	25	25
Total including LULUCF	25	25	25	25	25	23	25	24	25	25	25

Note: The colour intensity implies the degree of completeness. Dark green = high level of completeness, light green = lower level of completeness.

Table 2.3 displays the completeness of mandatory reported numeric emissions data or notation keys by gas for each Member State (under the WEM scenario in Table 1a), for the 2025 reporting cycle. Table 2.4 reports the same information by sector, for each Member State, in 2025. The presented percentages reflect the completeness of reporting for a given gas (respectively category), with 100% indicating full reporting completeness. It is worth noting that some specific gas-sector categories, such as CO₂ emissions from category “3.A. Enteric Fermentation”, are not included in this completeness analysis as certain gases do not occur in certain sector categories. The table cells are color-coded, with green indicating high completeness (100%) and red denoting the low completeness (0%).

The average completeness across all Member States and gases in 2025 remained very high, apart from Belgium and Romania, who did not provide an updated submission at the time of writing this report. A few gaps were identified where neither numerical values nor notation keys were reported, most notably by Denmark, Malta, and the Netherlands. Comparable completeness levels were observed when assessing the data by sector.

In 2023, only Italy achieved a 100% completeness on all categories, hence emerging as the Member State providing the most comprehensive projections in terms of categories. In 2025, no Member State achieved 100% completeness across all categories.

Table 2.3 Completeness of mandatory reported numeric emissions data or notation keys per gas, WEM scenario in Table 1a

MS	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O	SF ₆	NF ₃	HFC	PFC	Unspecified	ESR	ETS	Total
AT	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
BE	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
BG	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
CY	95%	97%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	50%	96%
CZ	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
DE	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
DK	100%	79%	67%	40%	0%	40%	50%	0%	83%	47%	78%
EE	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	99%
EL	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
ES	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	96%	67%	100%
FI	100%	97%	80%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	94%	94%	100%
FR	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	96%	94%	100%
HR	97%	97%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	97%
HU	98%	98%	80%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	96%	94%	99%
IE	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
IT	97%	100%	80%	90%	90%	90%	90%	90%	94%	89%	96%
LT	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
LU	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
LV	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
MT	98%	97%	80%	100%	70%	100%	100%	70%	93%	53%	94%
NL	100%	100%	78%	100%	100%	100%	90%	0%	96%	94%	100%
PL	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
PT	98%	98%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	96%	94%	90%
RO	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
SE	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
SI	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	94%	100%
SK	100%	100%	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	96%	94%	100%

Table 2.4 Completeness of mandatory reported numeric emissions data or notation keys per sector, WEM scenario in Table 1a

Country	1. Energy	2. Industrial processes	3. Agriculture	4. Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF, reported emissions and removals) [9]	5. Waste	Total excluding LULUCF	Total including LULUCF	Memo items
AT	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
BE	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
BG	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
CY	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
CZ	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
DE	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
DK	100%	82%	100%	75%	100%	82%	82%	100%
EE	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
EL	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
ES	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
FI	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
FR	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
HR	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
HU	100%	100%	100%	0%	100%	100%	100%	100%
IE	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
IT	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
LT	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
LU	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
LV	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
MT	100%	73%	80%	50%	100%	82%	82%	100%
NL	100%	91%	100%	75%	100%	91%	91%	100%
PL	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
PT	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
RO	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
SE	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
SI	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%
SK	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%

2.2.4 Completeness of time series and gap-filling

Table 2.5 delineates the completeness of time series reported by Member States in the 2025 mandatory reporting cycle for “Total without LULUCF” for Total GHGs in the “With Existing Measures (WEM)” scenarios. The table also identifies where interpolation or extrapolation was performed by the ETC CM and specifies the years to which these methods were applied. It should be noted that results may differ for other sectors, scenarios, and gases.

In the 2025 reporting cycle, 24 Member States provided complete data for the mandatory years 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, and 2050. However, several Member States — including Austria, Cyprus, Germany, Greece, France, Croatia, Hungary, Luxembourg, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, and Slovenia — did not submit data for the additional mandatory year 2055, which was therefore gap-filled by the ETC CM. Malta reported only up to 2040 and did not provide all mandatory years. Reporting of intermediate years was voluntary. 12 Member States required gap-filling of intermediate years between the reference year and 2050. When considering the complete time series up to 2055, all Member States except five required gap-filling of intermediate years. Only Denmark, Estonia, Spain, Ireland, and Lithuania did not require any gap-filling of mandatory nor intermediate years.

Two Member States, Belgium and Romania, did not submit updated projections in 2025 during the QA/QC procedure. Consequently, complete gap-filling was required for these countries to ensure the consistency and completeness of the EU27 dataset. The ETC CM developed country-specific approaches in

coordination with the EEA and the European Commission. Further details on the methodologies applied for these two Member States are presented in Box 2.1.

In comparison, during the 2023 mandatory reporting cycle, all Member States had submitted GHG projections for all mandatory years (2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, and 2050) and 15 Member States had voluntarily reported projections for all intermediate years.

Table 2.5 Completeness of time series for Total without LULUCF (Total GHGs, WEM) as reported in the final submissions

WEM/ Total GHGs	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026-2029	2030	2031-2034	2035	2036-2039	2040	2041-2044	2045	2046-2049	2050	2051-2054	2055	
AT						BY																
BE			BY																			
BG							BY															
CY						BY																
CZ						BY																
DE							BY															
DK							BY															
EE						BY																
EL						BY																
ES							BY															
FI						BY																
FR						BY																
HR						BY																
HU			BY																			
IE							BY															
IT							BY															
LT						BY																
LU					BY																	
LV						BY																
MT						BY											E			E		
NL						BY																
PL			BY																			
PT						BY																
RO							BY		E		E		E		E		E		E		E	
SE							BY															
SI						BY																
SK						BY																

Legend:

	reported
BY	base year
I	gap-filling of intermediate years
E	extrapolation of mandatory information
	Reporting not mandatory

In addition, it should be noted that the ETC CM carried out corrections, such as the correction of sums of parent categories, which did not match the sum of sub-categories as reported by Member States (for more detailed information on the sum check see chapter 2.3.5). Another typical corrective action by the ETC CM was the deletion of figures reported for historical years when no projections were available, because this would cause a jump in the time series in the EU projections (see also section 2.3.3).

For countries that did not report the WAM scenario, the ETC CM applied gap-filling using WEM data. In total, gap-filling was performed for 22 Member States for at least one year, gas, or category. In most cases, the WAM scenario and the gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and F-gases) were subject to the same corrections as the WEM scenario, as errors are usually systematic.

A summary of all corrections and gap-fillings during the 2025 cycle can be found in [Annex 1](#).

2.3 Consistency and Comparability

2.3.1 Units

The QA/QC unit check ensures that the projections are reported in the correct units in line with the reporting template. Figure 2.5 illustrates this check by displaying the number of Member States which submitted correct units, and the number of Member States which deviated from this requirement.

In general, consistency of units deteriorated a little in 2025. Eight Member State used incorrect units in Table 1a, 6 in Table 1b Part 2, and 7 in Table 1b Part 3. In comparison, in the 2023 reporting cycle, five deviations were identified in Table 1a, 1 in Table 1b Part 2, and 2 in Table 1b Part 3. The issues were clarified during the QA/QC procedure and in those cases in which an incorrect unit was applied, the countries provided a resubmission or clarifications for adjustments.

Figure 2.5 Number of Member States which reported the correct units in the initial submission

2.3.2 Reference year

Figure 2.6 and Table 2.6 report which year was chosen as reference by Member States in the 2025 reporting cycle. It is important to note that Belgium and Romania are excluded from the figure and table as they did not provide a submission during the 2025 QA/QC procedure.

During the QA/QC procedure in 2025, most Member States (13 out of 25) selected 2022 as their reference year, while eight Member States selected 2023. A few Member States opted for earlier reference years: 2019 was selected by Hungary and 2020 by Poland. Two Member States reported different reference years across tables: Luxembourg used 2017 for Table 1b and 2021 for Table 1a, while Slovenia applied 2020 for Table 1a and 2022 for Table 1b.

In comparison, in 2023, the predominant reference year choices among Member States were 2020 and 2021, selected by eight countries each. Seven Member States opted for 2019 as the reference year, while the remaining four countries – Poland, Slovenia, Luxembourg, and France – chose 2018, 2017, and 2015, respectively.

Figure 2.6 Reference year reported by Member States in Table 1a

Table 2.6 Reference year selected by the Member States

Member State	Base year	Member State	Base year	Member State	Base year
AT	2023	ES	2023	LV	2022
BE		FI	2022	MT	2022
BG	2023	FR	2022	NL	2022
CY	2022	HR	2022	PL	2020
CZ	2022	HU	2019	PT	2022
DE	2023	IE	2023	RO	
DK	2023	IT	2023	SE	2023
EE	2022	LT	2022	SI	2020/2022
EL	2022	LU	2017/2021	SK	2022

It is important to note that a crucial quality criterion lies in the consistency of time series between projections and historical data (inventories), ensuring that projections are founded on a recent inventory version. Simply knowing the reference year is insufficient to gauge if projections rely on an updated dataset.

Consequently, under the new reporting regulations, it is mandatory for Member States to specify the inventory submission version forming the basis of their projections. Table 2.7 therefore presents the GHG inventory versions submitted by the Member States in the 2025 reporting cycle. This table reveals that 17 Member States have reported GHG projections which are based on the 2024 inventory version, while 10 Member States based their GHG projections on the updated GHG inventory data submitted in 2025.

Table 2.7 Inventory versions on which the GHG projections are based

Member State	Inventory version	Member State	Inventory version	Member State	Inventory version
AT	2025	ES	2025	LV	2024
BE	N/A	FI	2025	MT	2024
BG	2025	FR	2024	NL	2024
CY	2024	HR	2024	PL	2023
CZ	2024	HU	2024	PT	2024
DE	2025	IE	2025	RO	N/A
DK	2024	IT	2025	SE	2025
EE	2024	LT	2024	SI	2023
EL	2024	LU	2025	SK	2024

The reference year chosen for the Union GHG projections in 2025 was 2023, which was used by eight out of 25 Member States for projections in the 2025 reporting cycle. Therefore, the Union GHG projections was built using the 2023-year inventory version of their emissions of these eight Member States and the projected 2023 emissions from the other 17 Member States. In comparison, the reference year chosen for the Union GHG projections in 2023 was 2021, which was used by eight Member States as their reference year for their projections.

2.3.3 Time series consistency

In previous cycles, the ETC CM identified instances where certain Member States reported historical values from the GHG inventory when GHG projections were not available. This practice led to artificial jumps in the time series when aggregating Member States' projection data for EU27 projections. In response to this, a new check was introduced since 2021 to ensure that Member States refrain from reporting values in the time series for sectors and gases lacking projections.

In 2025, 23 out of 25 reporting Member States received a finding related to the time series consistency check, with the exceptions being Bulgaria and Slovakia. Despite this, several corrections were necessary to achieve a cohesive and consistent EU-aggregated dataset.

The most common issues were related to Member States not reporting the 2055 mandatory year. Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Germany, Greece, France, Croatia, Hungary, Luxembourg, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, and Slovenia required gap-filling to extend their datasets to 2055, as only 13 Member States reported data for the last mandatory projection year. This was achieved by applying the 2050 values as constant values for the period 2051-2055.

Additionally, blanks and zeroes were treated as NK where this was the case to ensure consistency, and adjustments were required to remove reference year data in cases where projections were unavailable.

These corrections ensured a consistent and reliable EU-27 dataset, maintaining the integrity of trends across Member States while accommodating variations in reporting practices.

2.3.4 ETS and ESR emissions

Projected emissions are systematically reported for Emissions Trading System (ETS) and Effort Sharing (ESR) emissions in each source category. In the QA/QC process, the analysis focuses on ensuring the accurate linkage of projections to historical ETS and ESR emissions and maintaining a coherent development of ETS and ESR emissions in Member State projections.

Following the QA/QC procedure, the ETS and ESR emissions from Member State projections are aggregated to form an EU projection. This aggregated projection is crucial for monitoring the impacts of EU policies aimed at addressing climate change, and the projection data find application in numerous reports and indicators produced by the EEA and the ETC CM.

In Figure 2.7, a comparison is made between historical and projected Effort Sharing emissions for the reference years used by each of the Member States in the 2025 reporting cycle. For this cycle, the ESR comparison employed the original submission as the mandatory reference year. The average difference between historical and projected ESR emissions in 2025 was -2.5%, whereas it was -1.42% in 2023. In 2025, Denmark (-44%), Czechia (-8.5%), Finland (-7.7%), Greece (-6.3%), and Germany (+6.2%) all presented significant variations between historical emissions and those reported in the projections. Differently, in 2023, significant variations were displayed by Bulgaria (-18.7%), Czechia (-7%) and Hungary (-6.5%).

Figure 2.7 Relative difference between historic and projected Effort Sharing emissions for reference years

Changes in ETS splits, representing alterations in the proportion of ETS emissions relative to total emissions, were calculated across the projected timeline to scrutinize the evolution of ETS and ESR emission projections and ensure time series consistency. Member States typically provide explanations for such changes, particularly when they are significant. For instance, in smaller countries, the closure or start-up of a single plant can heavily impact the share of ETS emissions, leading to considerable changes in projected ETS splits from one year to the next.

Table 2.8 highlights increases or decreases in ETS splits for the 2025 cycle, colour-coded based on the magnitude of the change.

Substantial changes in the share of ETS emissions relative to total emissions were observed for Denmark and Greece for 2025-2030 (72% and 50% respectively), for Slovenia for 2030-2035 (55% respectively), and for Bulgaria, Estonia, and Greece for 2045-2050 (82%, 65%, and 64% respectively). It is important to note that the results for Malta for 2030–2035 present a misleading picture, as the ETS totals submitted did not include emissions from the Energy sector. This issue was subsequently corrected during the QA/QC process.

Upon examining individual Member States, Bulgaria demonstrated the largest change in absolute value in the share of ETS emissions relative to total (44%) averaged on all five periods, while Luxemburg exhibited the smallest change at 1%. When analysed by periods, the 2025-2030 period displayed the most significant change in absolute value at 24%, followed by 2030-2035 at 18%.

In comparison, outliers for the 2023 cycle included Germany and Denmark, which exhibited noteworthy changes for 2025-2030 (53% and 94% respectively); Denmark for 2035-2040 (66%); Estonia and Finland for 2040-2045 (92% and 94% respectively). The 2045-2050 period displayed the most significant changes at 55% on average (primarily attributed to Finland), followed by 2025-2030 at 18% on average (primarily attributed to Germany and Denmark).

Table 2.8 Changes in ETS splits from 2025 to 2055 in WEM scenario

Member State	2025-2030	2030-2035	2035-2040	2040-2045	2045-2050	2050-2055
AT	15%	-1%	-3%	4%	-1%	NA
BG	39%	30%	36%	34%	82%	0%
CY	27%	4%	18%	-15%	2%	NA
CZ	43%	15%	16%	17%	9%	0%
DE	38%	25%	19%	13%	2%	NA
DK	72%	3%	2%	-25%	-10%	0%
EE	22%	25%	15%	29%	65%	21%
EL	50%	30%	36%	9%	64%	NA
ES	-2%	-7%	11%	10%	14%	12%
FI	25%	39%	48%	4%	3%	0%
FR	12%	1%	1%	1%	-5%	NA
HR	-5%	10%	11%	5%	5%	NA
HU	31%	11%	2%	-15%	-2%	NA
IE	22%	15%	7%	2%	9%	4%
IT	10%	18%	0%	9%	-4%	0%
LT	10%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%
LU	2%	2%	2%	1%	0%	NA
LV	6%	8%	28%	-1%	-5%	NA
MT	44%	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
NL	36%	14%	6%	20%	10%	10%
PL	28%	30%	24%	27%	28%	NA
PT	21%	23%	18%	15%	11%	NA
SE	40%	7%	17%	2%	0%	0%
SI	0%	55%	-16%	-7%	-13%	NA
SK	2%	2%	2%	1%	1%	1%

The reporting of ETS and ESR emissions continuously improved since 2015 and became considerably more detailed in the 2017, 2019, 2021, 2023, and now the 2025 submission years.

In the 2025 QA/QC process cycles, nearly all 25 Member States correctly did not report emissions from 1A3a in the ETS, with only Hungary showcasing minor inconsistencies from potential allocation issues for domestic aviation. Furthermore, none of the eleven Member States reported NF3 emissions in ESR/ETS

emissions. However, Lithuania did report CO₂ recovery and urea production under category 2.B Chemical industry under ETS emissions to ensure consistency with the calculation of national purposes and targets, which caused Total ETS emissions being higher than the Total GHGs for category 2.B. Chemical industry.

In the 2023 cycle, regarding absolute ESR emissions, all Member States subtracted domestic aviation from total GHG emissions to calculate ESR emissions in the final dataset. In addition, most Member States correctly implemented the inclusion of NF₃ emissions in the Effort Sharing Regulation (from 2021). Member States were asked to exclude emissions on ETS aviation from the ETS emissions to allow the calculation of a consistent set of stationary ETS emissions.

2.3.5 Accuracy and transparency

The sum check was introduced in 2017 and has been further elaborated over the years for the new LULUCF tables 1b and 5a.

In the 2025 cycle, the sum check did not reveal issues for most of the 25 reporting Member States. However, for six Member States – Cyprus, Germany, Spain, Poland, Portugal, and Slovenia – the check identified inconsistencies that required follow-up during the QA/QC procedure. In total, 10 questions were raised through the QA/QC process, as some findings covered multiple sectors, years, gases, and/or scenarios.

For three of these six Member States (Germany, Portugal, and Slovenia), the issues were caused by manual errors and subsequently corrected by the countries themselves. For the remaining three – Cyprus, Spain, and Poland – corrective actions were required from the ETC CM. For Cyprus and Spain, the sum of individual GHGs did not match the reported totals for both “with” and “without LULUCF”. In Poland’s case, the inconsistency concerned the ‘5. Waste’ sector for N₂O emissions, where the sum of subsectors and individual gases did not add up to the parent sector total across all mandatory years under the WEM scenario, as well as the sum of individual N₂O did not match the reported totals for both “with” and “without LULUCF”.

In the previous mandatory reporting cycle 2023, no sum check issues were identified for Belgium, Greece, Spain, Croatia, Ireland, Luxembourg, Sweden, Slovenia, and Slovakia, while the remaining 19 Member States experienced at least one issue. The issues were sometimes aggregated in case they applied to multiple sectors, years, GHGs and/or scenarios, resulting in 27 questions in total.

Although the ETC CM experts used a clear threshold value for the checks, some Member States were informed about a difference that was below the threshold value. These instances often related to manual control which excludes that small differences were caused by rounding, with the ETC CM subsequently posing a question to the Member States to explain. In all cases where the difference was larger than the threshold value, corrective action was applied by the Member State (including a resubmission) or by the ETC CM.

2.3.6 Outliers and trends

The evaluation of outliers and trends in the projections relies on four distinct checks, utilising information from reported projections in 2025 as in mandatory years, inventory data, and previously documented projection details. The analysis of trends and outliers becomes challenging when there is a scarcity of data points in the time series, particularly when intermediate years are not reported. For smaller Member States, changes in emissions can exhibit more pronounced fluctuations, especially in sectors where emissions are predominantly influenced by a limited number of point sources.

These checks operate under the assumption of linear trends and employ threshold values to signal deviations from historical and prior projection trends. The linear trend line is also employed for outlier

identification, pinpointing emissions in specific years that significantly differ from expectations based on the linear trend line. It is crucial to emphasize that the findings from these checks do not necessarily indicate errors in projections; instead, they highlight the necessity for further clarification. This clarification can be achieved through visual inspection of the data by the reviewer, consultation of the technical report, or posing a question to the Member State.

Instances where a potential issue did not result in a question to the Member States include:

- Non-linear trends: Visual inspection reveals no outliers, attributing the issue to a non-linear trend in projected emissions.
- Trends explained in the report: If the technical report provides a comprehensive explanation for the identified trends.

For 2025, a total of 25 questions were raised across all checks, including 18 for trends and 2 for outliers, and 5 for projected trend, covering 14 Member States from the 25. These evaluations ensured consistency and reliability while minimizing redundant queries through aggregated questioning. Nearly all the questions were explained by the Member States, and in most cases the issues were highlighted due to a lack of supporting information in the technical report. As such, for these questions, the general recommendation was to describe the main trends of the emissions in the technical report.

For the 2023 cycle, a similar number of potential issues could not be resolved by inspection of the data or consultation of the technical report. This resulted in a total of 26 questions to the Member States for outliers and trend checks combined.

2.3.7 Recalculations

When projected emissions displayed substantial deviations from previous projections without accompanying information in the report, transparency considerations led to requests for explanations from Member State experts. These experts were advised to include clarifications for recalculations in the technical reports.

During the 2025 cycle, in total, 21 questions were raised to 21 Member States concerning the recalculation check, except for Austria, Estonia, Denmark and Ireland. Generally, the reasons related to more detailed information being available, updated assessments, or the use of new methodologies. Therefore, no corrective action from the ETC CM was conducted following these findings.

During 2023 cycle, a total of 18 questions related to the recalculation check were directed to eighteen distinct Member State. Typically, the primary reasons behind significantly altered projections involve modifications in PaMs, the adoption of different models or methodologies, and the introduction of new or revised data.

Conversely, this check also brings to light instances where submissions mirrored previous ones entirely, signifying a lack of updates in the projections – either no updates at all or only recalibrations to the latest emission inventory data. In both the 2025 and 2023 cycles, this was not the case for any of the Member States.

In Table 2.9.9, as part of the recalculation check, a comparison is made for total GHG emissions without LULUCF in the WEM and WAM scenarios for the 2025 reporting cycle. This comparison specifically focuses on the years 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045 and 2050 (no comparison can be made for 2055 as the 2025 cycle was the first time this year was to be reported), contrasting them with the closest submission from 2023 for each respective country. The table is color-coded, ranging from green to red, to visually represent negative and positive differences in the comparison.

The largest positive differences under both the WEM and WAM scenarios are observed for Malta for 2045 (93.4% for WAM and 92% for WEM) and 2050 (94% for WAM and 93.6% for WEM) respectively. The largest negative difference is observed for Estonia under the WEM scenario (-35%) for 2045 and for Slovenia under the WAM scenario (-9.2%) for 2050. It is important to note that the results for Malta for present a misleading picture, as the total GHG emissions submitted did not include emissions from the Energy sector after 2040. This issue was subsequently corrected during the QA/QC process.

Table 2.9 Recalculation check, comparison total GHG emissions without LULUCF for WEM and WAM scenarios for 2025-2050 of the 2025 submission against the 2023 submission

MS	WAM						WEM					
	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
AT	3.6%	18.2%	26.0%	37.3%	48.9%	54.5%	5.7%	10.5%	12.5%	15.9%	22.1%	24.7%
BE												
BG	24.6%	43.8%	46.2%	48.6%	58.1%	73.2%	24.9%	44.5%	47.8%	50.3%	59.5%	74.1%
CY	-5.7%	16.1%	22.1%	31.6%	21.2%	18.3%	-13.2%	-0.6%	-0.3%	4.8%	-8.0%	-15.3%
CZ	14.3%	26.0%	32.1%	44.1%	53.1%	61.6%	9.0%	20.7%	22.6%	26.4%	28.1%	23.2%
DE	9.1%	-6.6%	-9.0%	-9.1%	-2.9%	-2.5%	10.7%	0.8%	5.5%	4.6%	10.9%	9.1%
DK							1.7%	12.1%	20.0%	19.3%	25.3%	27.4%
EE							3.2%	-0.1%	1.9%	5.7%	-35.0%	-4.7%
EL	4.8%	20.7%	35.2%	52.1%	64.0%	79.1%	4.8%	20.7%	35.2%	52.1%	64.0%	79.1%
ES	0.6%	0.6%					11.1%	12.6%	12.7%	26.1%	38.4%	43.7%
FI							-4.1%	-12.7%	-2.3%	5.3%	-7.7%	-23.9%
FR	6.3%	20.4%					3.3%	5.6%	6.7%	10.4%	13.7%	15.5%
HR	1.3%	13.0%	20.6%	37.0%	42.5%	50.2%	-0.4%	-0.5%	-0.8%	0.3%	3.3%	7.6%
HU	0.5%	13.6%	24.8%	33.9%	46.2%	64.7%	-0.8%	2.9%	9.6%	10.1%	10.9%	16.3%
IE	1.7%	-6.0%	-4.1%	-9.1%	-6.9%	-0.4%	5.8%	1.6%	4.3%	3.7%	6.8%	10.0%
IT	2.9%	18.5%	22.9%	26.0%	36.6%	42.4%	-1.8%	2.2%	2.7%	4.4%	8.5%	11.0%
LT	-0.3%	0.9%	2.2%	1.9%	1.5%	1.0%	1.1%	2.1%	3.3%	3.4%	3.1%	2.7%
LU	5.0%	-2.3%	-4.9%	7.2%	13.5%	18.0%	0.2%	-0.9%	-3.7%	-6.5%	-8.8%	-9.8%
LV	13.3%	13.5%	13.0%	25.8%	29.7%	29.4%	9.4%	12.2%	10.1%	15.2%	24.1%	25.7%
MT	6.1%	29.6%	57.9%	61.5%	93.4%	94.0%	6.1%	24.6%	49.5%	56.9%	92.0%	93.6%
NL	3.9%	6.8%	13.9%	21.0%			3.8%	3.9%	11.5%	20.3%	26.1%	31.7%
PL	6.6%	24.2%	30.1%	40.1%	49.7%	55.5%	14.3%	30.0%	37.4%	40.7%	49.4%	55.8%
PT	14.5%	5.7%	-4.9%	0.2%	12.0%	0.6%	16.3%	-3.5%	0.8%	11.6%	35.8%	46.4%
RO												
SE							-11.2%	-9.8%	-13.5%	-2.1%	5.3%	9.1%
SI	0.4%	-1.3%	19.1%	18.2%	9.2%	-9.2%	3.7%	4.1%	28.8%	30.0%	36.2%	40.7%
SK	12.5%	13.9%	20.4%	30.4%	34.9%	36.6%	15.1%	12.7%	13.9%	17.3%	18.9%	20.1%

Note: Negative values means that the submission in 2023 was lower as the new submission in 2025 (indicated by green colour). When the 2025 are lower than the 2023 this is highlighted in red.

2.3.8 WEM/WAM/WOM check

Ensures consistency and adherence to the expected order of emissions levels across scenarios, WOM emissions should be equal to or greater than WEM emissions, and WEM emissions should be equal to or greater than WAM scenario. In case Member States submit a WOM scenario, it was assessed if emissions in the WOM scenario are equal to or higher than emissions in the WEM scenario. Similarly, when Member States submitted a WAM scenario, it was assessed whether emissions in the WEM scenario are equal to or higher than emissions in the WAM scenario. For sectors and gases where such equality or higher emissions were not observed, clarification questions were sent to the respective Member State.

In 2025, instances where projected emissions under the WAM scenario were higher than those under the WEM scenario – contrary to the definitions of these scenarios – were identified for 18 of the 25 reporting Member States. This resulted in 18 questions to these Member States. It is important to note that these findings were identified by sector and gas, and in most cases the total GHGs were in line with the definitions of the scenarios. The only exceptions of Member States where no findings were identified where projected emissions under the WAM scenario were higher than those under the WEM scenario were Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Greece, Ireland, Malta, and Sweden (and excluding Belgium and

Romania, which were not included in the QA/QC process due to non-submission of projections data in 2025).

For Czechia and Slovenia, the issue was resolved through the resubmission of corrected data. For all other affected Member States, clarifications were provided explaining the causes of the inconsistencies, and it was recommended that these cases – where WAM emissions exceed WEM emissions – and their underlying rationale be documented in the accompanying technical report.

In the 2023 mandatory reporting year, a similar situation was observed for 16 Member States, leading to 18 questions. All Member States except Romania and Slovenia received at least one question. In most cases, Member States provided satisfactory explanations for the observed inconsistencies.

The reasons for higher WAM emissions compared to WEM emissions varied in both the 2025 and 2023 cycles, ranging from model-related errors to considerations of PaMs. For instance, discrepancies might result from assumptions such as an allowance for more flights under WAM, higher biomass utilization, or an increased share of installed heat pumps. While the primary objective of this check was not necessarily to enforce corrective actions, some questions did lead to error corrections and subsequent resubmissions.

2.3.9 LULUCF reporting

Under the reporting framework established by the Governance Regulation, the requirements for the LULUCF sector include detailed projections and accounting information. These provisions were introduced to ensure that Member States report on emissions and removals consistent with the inclusion of LULUCF in the EU's climate mitigation target.

The Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1208 specifies two alternative tables—Table 1b or Table 5a—for reporting LULUCF projections, and Table 5b for cumulative projected accounting results. Member States are required to complete one of the projection tables (1b or 5a), while Table 5b is used to report cumulative projected accounting outcomes for LULUCF accounting categories and ESR cumulative projections over two accounting periods.

Table 1b also contains two mandatory summary tables that must be completed regardless of the Member State's choice between Tables 1b or 5a. While some sections of these tables are voluntary, the ETC CM regularly reminds Member States to provide complete submissions to ensure comparability and consistency across Member States.

Some Member States opted not to report all three gases, aligning with the IPCC Guidelines. This allowance is made in cases where specific management practices or land use/land use changes do not occur nationally. For instance, the occurrence of methane (CH₄) due to forest fires or drainage of organic soils might not be applicable in all Member States and, consequently, may not be reported.

To ensure comprehensive coverage, the ETC CM systematically cross-checks all main sectors and categories with the GHG inventory. Where discrepancies arise (e.g., a category/gas combination is present in the inventory but missing in projections), clarification requests are sent to the relevant Member State.

During the 2025 cycle, all the 25 reporting Member States (i.e. all but Belgium and Romania) provided information for all gases and the total in both Table 1b Part 2 and Part 3 (Table 2.10).

Table 2.10 Reported summary tables (part 2 and part 3 of table 1b) for the LULUCF sector

Member State	Table 1b part 2				Table 1b part 3			
	Total GHGs (ktCO ₂ e)	CO ₂ (ktCO ₂ e)	CH ₄ (ktCO ₂ e)	N ₂ O (ktCO ₂ e)	Total GHGs (ktCO ₂ e)	CO ₂ (ktCO ₂ e)	CH ₄ (ktCO ₂ e)	N ₂ O (ktCO ₂ e)
AT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
BG	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CY	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CZ	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
DE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
DK	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
EE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
EL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ES	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FI	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
HR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
HU	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
IE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
IT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
LT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
LU	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
LV	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
NL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
PL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
PT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SI	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SK	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

In the last mandatory reporting year (2023), among the 27 Member States, 23 reported LULUCF projections, with the four non-reporting Member States being Bulgaria, Denmark, Spain, and Ireland. Out of the 23 reporting Member States, 20 provided information for all gases and the total in both Table 1b Part 2 and Part 3. The Member States with some missing information were consistent across both tables and for the same gas—methane (CH₄), with Belgium, Luxembourg, and Malta being the Member States in question.

2.3.10 Sensitivity analysis

Member States must provide sensitivity scenario results in a standardized format, covering sectoral totals (Total without LULUCF, Total ETS, Total ESR, and LULUCF). In addition, key parameters must be reported in a separate table.

These sensitivity tables (Tables 6 and 7) allow assessment of the robustness of projections under different assumptions. Reporting is mandatory and it has gradually expanded as Member States strengthen their modelling frameworks.

In 2025 cycle, 17 of the 25 reporting Member States submitted data for sensitivity scenarios, as detailed in Table 2.11. On average, these 17 Member States reported 4.3 scenarios in Table 6 and 4.0 scenarios in Table 7. Germany reported the most scenarios for Table 6 (15 scenarios), and both Germany and Spain for Table 7 (12 scenarios). As these tables were introduced in 2021, ongoing efforts aim to address discrepancies and strengthen data validation in future cycles.

In 2023, 19 Member States contributed sensitivity scenarios to either Table 6 or 7, with an average of four scenarios per table – an increase from three in the preceding cycle. Spain led the sensitivity scenarios in Table 6, while Germany excelled in parameter reporting with nine submissions, followed by Spain with eight.

Table 2.11 Overview of reporting of sensitivity analysis scenarios

Member State	Number of scenarios reported	
	Emissions (Table 6)	Parameters (Table 7)
AT	2	2
BE		
BG	0	0
CY	2	2
CZ	4	4
DE	15	12
DK	0	0
EE	3	3
EL	2	2
ES	12	12
FI	2	2
FR	2	2
HR	4	4
HU	0	0
IE	2	1
IT	0	0
LT	3	3
LU	0	0
LV	6	6
MT	8	7
NL	1	1
PL	0	0
PT	0	0
RO		
SE	1	1
SI	4	4
SK	0	0

2.4 Parameters

2.4.1 Overview of reported parameters

The reporting of parameters is part of the GHG projection reporting in Reportnet3, whereby only those parameters which are used in projections shall be reported. This explains why the reporting is not consistent across Member States, which also can report on additional parameters other than the ones included the template. In 2025, all Member States except Belgium and Romania reported parameters, totalling in 292, compared to 156 in 2024 (which was a non-mandatory reporting year). It is important to note that not all Member States report all parameters, as their relevance varies based on their application in projections. Parameters like gross domestic product (GDP), European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) carbon price and population find broader applications in general models, while others are employed in specific, often more sophisticated models.

Figure 2.8 highlights parameters reported by more than 14 EU Member States in the 2025 cycle. This criterion is met for 33 parameters, as opposed to 38 parameters reported last year. Notably, parameters

related to population EU ETS prices, and GDP receive widespread reporting from most Member States. Additionally, frequently reported parameters are predominantly associated with Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use (AFOLU), such as nitrogen input, indicating their significance in projecting the agricultural sector. These are followed by parameters linked to the economy and energy, such as fuel import prices and carbon prices, along with various indicators related to households, waste, and the transportation system.

Figure 2.8 Parameters reported by more than 14 Member States

Of the 259 parameters reported by less than half of the EU Member States, 242 are utilised by only one country once. Czechia, Estonia, Luxembourg and the Netherlands are the countries using many specific parameters not used by other countries. Czechia has many specific parameters linked to combined heat and power plants, Estonia’s are linked to the AFOLU sector, Luxembourg’s linked to energy (renewables) and agriculture sector, and the Netherlands have specific parameters for the industry sector. Netherlands is also the only country, which reports on the CO2 emissions capture from bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and fossil sources. This diversity in parameter usage underscores the specialized nature of certain parameters, while others find broader applicability across multiple contexts.

Due to this diversity, quality checks are not carried out for all parameters, but only for the ones most used and for which the EC provided recommendation to allow for better consistency across Europe (e.g. EU ETS prices, fossil fuel prices, GDP, population). The checking includes a unit check (and conversion if needed), a comparison of historic years with data in Eurostat, and a comparison with the EC recommended parameters.

2.4.2 Most common parameter issues

The parameter table (IR Annex XXV Table 3) was submitted by 25 Member States. The comprehensive overview given in Table 2.12 Heat Map of QA/QC procedure and most common issues of the parameter checks Table 2.12 summarises the QA/QC process for each Member State and the reported key parameters. A few follow-ups were needed for the parameter population. There were a few countries which did not use the default units (purple), so the unit was converted by the ETC CM experts or Member States resubmitted values or explanations were provided by the Member States that solved the issue. The overview also shows that GDP was not an input parameter in projections of four Member States and that net electricity imports was not used in the projections of ten Member States.

In most cases, the communication with Member States successfully solved the issues regarding the submitted parameters. This was the case when e.g. data consistent with the surrogate data was resubmitted or when an explanation of the differences was given by Member State experts. Explanations why GDP was not in line with surrogate data were mainly that Member States used data from their statistical office which is different to Eurostat or because conversion rates differed between the Member States from the data used by the reviewers. However, some issues could not be solved as there was no reply from the Member State on the findings. In some cases, Member States did not submit reference year values or the reference year in the first submission, so it was asked for it in the communication log. After the resubmission of these values and years, in some cases a deviation from reference data was found, but this was not followed up due to time constraints.

A relatively large number of issues with parameter values was resolved through explanation by Member States. Although reasons usually relate to the use of national datasets, and slight differences in e.g. exchange rates, it shows that this is still a source of uncertainty.

Table 2.12 Heat Map of QA/QC procedure and most common issues of the parameter checks

Member State	Population	GDP abs.	Net Electricity Imports	Final Energy consumption	Gross Electricity Generation	Number of households	Dairy Cattle
Austria	Green	Purple	Green	Green	Orange	Green	Green
Belgium*	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Bulgaria	Green	Orange	Yellow	Green	Orange	Green	Green
Croatia	Purple	Orange	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green
Cyprus	Yellow	Purple	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green
Czechia	Purple	Orange	Green	Green	Orange	Yellow	Green
Denmark	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Orange	Yellow	Green
Estonia	Green	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green
Finland	Green	Orange	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green
France	Purple	Purple	Purple	Orange	Green	Orange	Green
Germany	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Green	Yellow	Green
Greece	Purple	Purple	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Hungary	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Ireland	Green	Orange	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
Italy	Purple	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Orange
Latvia	Green	Orange	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Lithuania	Green	Orange	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
Luxembourg	Green	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
Malta	Green	Orange	Yellow	Orange	Yellow	Green	Green
Netherlands	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	Green	Green	Orange
Poland	Purple	Orange	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Orange
Portugal	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
Romania**							
Slovakia	Green	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Yellow
Slovenia	Green	Orange	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Purple	Green
Spain	Purple	Purple	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green
Sweden	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green

Legend: * Belgium did not provide a submission in 2025, data was gap-filled with 2024 submission
 ** Romania did not provide a submission in 2025, and parameters have not been gap-filled

Colour code:

value in line with surrogate data
value not in line with surrogate data
no use of default unit -> corrected by reviewer
no values submitted / values not used

Note: Data of Member States was checked against surrogate datasets from Eurostat (Eurostat 2023a-c) a) Population – Eurostat demo_pjan; b) GDP - Eurostat nama_10_gdp; c) net electricity import - Eurostat nrg_cb_e; d) Households – Eurostat lfst_hhnhtych, e) Dairy cattle – Eurostat apro_mt_lscatl. Threshold for historic parameter check: deviation to historic data from Eurostat for all parameters <2% except Households and Dairy Cattle <5% for all parameters in 2025

2.4.3 Deviation from recommended parameters

In line with the Implementing Regulation (Article 38(3)) to increase EU wide consistency of projections, the European Commission provided Member States with recommended supranational parameters on ETS carbon price, international oil and coal prices and other parameters e.g., international gas prices, GDP growth, population for the preparation of GHG projections (European Commission, 2025). Checks were carried out to understand whether Member States used the provided values (In general, it can be observed that the parameters related to population and international wholesale fuel prices for gas are the ones that Member States have followed the guidance mostly).

Not all Member States provided an explanation why recommended parameters were not taken into account but rather indicated that they had opted for reporting values from other modelling exercises. For example, Germany explained that the parameters were taken into account for the year 2030, but that it was decided to use different values for the other years from more recent publications, such as the International Energy Agency's (IEA) World Energy Outlook, which suggested lower fuel prices. A similar reasoning was provided by the Netherlands. In addition, some Member States used the values for the parameters used for their National Energy and Climate Plan projections, instead of the recommended parameters.

Table 2.13). The classification was made by setting deviation threshold for individual parameters. Note that it is possible that for two projection years parameters do not deviate, but for other projection years they do (e.g. when national parameters are available, but not for the full time series). In these instances, the ETC CM made an expert judgement if it can be assumed that the recommended parameters were used or not. In addition, it is possible that values happen to be in the same range as the recommended values, without actual use of the Commission's Guidance. Similarly, due to potential exchange rate issues of price data (ETC CM converts all monetary values to constant EUR2023 for the comparison), some parameters may have been classified as not following the Commission Guidance. It should be noted that in the 2025 QA/QC procedure, this check is of informative nature only and no follow up was made in case parameters deviated from the recommendations of the European Commission. The check was applied only on the parameters presented in the table below, using the reported data for the first mandatory year after the reference year, 2025¹.

In general, it can be observed that the parameters related to population and international wholesale fuel prices for gas are the ones that Member States have followed the guidance mostly.

Not all Member States provided an explanation why recommended parameters were not taken into account but rather indicated that they had opted for reporting values from other modelling exercises. For example, Germany explained that the parameters were taken into account for the year 2030, but that it was decided to use different values for the other years from more recent publications, such as the International Energy Agency's (IEA) World Energy Outlook, which suggested lower fuel prices. A similar reasoning was provided by the Netherlands. In addition, some Member States used the values for the parameters used for their National Energy and Climate Plan projections, instead of the recommended parameters.

¹ Numerous issues were found with the reference year and the starting year for reporting parameters. For this reason and aiming at having a complete EU dataset to be cross-checked, 2025 data was used for the comparison.

Table 2.13 Use of recommended parameters by the European Commission

Member State	GDP rel	Population	Fuel price - oil	Fuel price - gas	Fuel price - coal	ETS carbon price
Austria	no	partly	yes	yes	yes	yes
Belgium*	NR	partly	NR	NR	NR	NR
Bulgaria	NR	partly	no	no	no	no
Croatia	yes	yes	partly	yes	no	no
Cyprus	NR	NR	partly	yes	NR	partly
Czechia	NR	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Denmark	no	yes	no	yes	no	no
Estonia	no	no	yes	yes	yes	no
Finland	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
France	partly	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Germany	no	yes	no	partly	no	partly
Greece	NR	partly	no	no	NR	no
Hungary	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
Ireland	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Italy	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Latvia	no	no	yes	yes	no	yes
Lithuania	yes	yes	NR	NR	NR	no
Luxembourg	no	partly	yes	yes	yes	NR
Malta	no	yes	NR	NR	NR	no
Netherlands	NR	yes	no	no	no	no
Poland	no	partly	no	yes	no	no
Portugal	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Romania**						
Slovakia	NR	yes	NR	NR	NR	yes
Slovenia	no	yes	NR	NR	NR	NR
Spain	NR	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Sweden	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes

Note: * Belgium did not provide a submission in 2025, data was gap-filled with 2024 submission

** Romania did not provide a submission in 2025 and parameters have not been gap-filled

	Coal price	Gas price	Oil price	Carbon price	Population	GDP
Number Member States using guidance in 2025	11	16	12	11	13	3
Number Member States using guidance in 2024	6	6	8	5	12	3
Number Member States using guidance in 2023	3	2	4	2	4	1
Number Member States using guidance in 2021	3	4	4	8	10	1
Number Member States that used guidance in 2019	9	9	9	12	9	0
Number Member States that used guidance in 2017	9	8	10	11	6	3

Colour code:

NR	parameter not used for projections and therefore not reported (NR)
no	deviation to COM guidance > 3 % for prices >2 % for population and GDP until 2023 deviation to COM guidance >5% for all parameters in 2024 deviation to COM guidance >2% for all parameters in 2025
yes	deviation to COM guidance < 3 % for prices, < 2 % for population and GDP until 2023 deviation to COM guidance <5% for all parameters in 2024 deviation to COM guidance <2% for all parameters in 2025
partly	deviation to COM guidance >2% for some parameters in 2025

3 Specific analysis of new reporting elements

In the 2025 reporting cycle, several new updated reporting templates and elements have been introduced. These include the differentiation of the projected values of total CO₂ capture according to the source of emissions (biogenic vs. fossil fuel) in Table 3, the extended projection horizon to 2055, and the addition of two new sub-categories in Table 1a related to LULUCF (4.I Atmospheric deposition and 4.J Nitrogen leaching and run-off).

3.1 Biogenic CO₂ capture vs fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture (table 3)

While CO₂ capture itself is not a new reporting element, as it was already to be reported in table 1a in previous cycles, the 2025 reporting cycle introduced an important refinement. Member States are now required to indicate whether captured CO₂ originates from biogenic or fossil sources in table 3.

To align with the scope of inventory reporting, negative emissions can be directly incorporated into category values in table 1a. However, reporting in Table 3 on total CO₂ captured by type (BECCs vs fossil fuel) would then be deemed mandatory as a result. This is to allow data to be comparable and usable under the scope of the EU ETS, ESR, and LULUCF, where negative emissions are not in the legal scope and negative emissions will have to be removed from projections. As such, Member States who have incorporated negative emissions should include information on the biogenic and fossil fuel share / percentage as part of the additional information category in section 5, 'other parameters and variables', in Table 3.

Out of the 25 EU Member States that submitted GHG projections data, 9 Member States (33%) reported CO₂ capture data in table 1a in either the WEM or WAM scenarios (Figure 3.1). These were Finland, Portugal, France, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Hungary, Germany, and Lithuania (Table 3.1). The remaining 16 Member States did not report CO₂ capture, and Belgium and Romania submitted no projections data in this cycle. This is consistent with the current limited deployment or planning of capture technologies in their national projections.

Figure 3.1 Reported CO₂ capture in table 1a in WEM or WAM scenarios

Table 3.1 Overview by Member State of reported CO₂ capture in table 1a in WEM or WAM scenarios

Member State	Reported CO ₂ Capture	Member State	Reported CO ₂ Capture	Member State	Reported CO ₂ Capture
AT	No	ES	No	LV	No
BE	N/A	FI	Yes	MT	No
BG	No	FR	Yes	NL	Yes
CY	No	HR	No	PL	No
CZ	No	HU	Yes	PT	Yes
DE	Yes	IE	No	RO	N/A
DK	No	IT	Yes	SE	No
EE	No	LT	Yes	SI	No
EL	Yes	LU	No	SK	No

The addition to distinguish between biogenic CO₂ capture and fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture in Table 3 represents a key step forward in capturing the diversity of carbon management technologies within national projections. The reporting of biogenic CO₂ capture versus fossil fuel CO₂ capture in Table 3 showed low completeness in the initial submissions and prior to the QA/QC process, with only one Member State (the Netherlands) initially providing this differentiation. Following QA/QC and subsequent clarifications, two Member States (Portugal and Lithuania) included the necessary information in table 3 as part of their resubmission, while the remaining Member States only provided more information or clarifications in the communication log (Figure 3.2). By the end of the QA/QC cycle, three Member States had distinguished biogenic CO₂ capture from fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture in Table 3 in their submission (Table 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Reported biogenic CO₂ capture vs fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture in table 3

Table 3.2 Overview by Member State of reported biogenic vs fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture in table 3

Member State	Reported biogenic vs fossil capture	Member State	Reported biogenic vs fossil capture	Member State	Reported biogenic vs fossil capture
AT	No	ES	No	LV	No
BE	N/A	FI	No	MT	No
BG	No	FR	No	NL	Yes
CY	No	HR	No	PL	No
CZ	No	HU	No	PT	Yes
DE	No	IE	No	RO	N/A
DK	No	IT	No	SE	No
EE	No	LT	Yes	SI	No
EL	No	LU	No	SK	No

The 2025 cycle therefore marks an important first step toward more systematic and transparent reporting of carbon capture technologies. While coverage remains limited, the QA/QC process demonstrated that targeted guidance and bilateral communication can significantly improve data quality. Continued refinement of reporting instructions and clearer definitions for BECCS-related categories will be essential to ensure consistency and comparability in future cycles.

3.2 Reporting of 2055 mandatory year

In the 2025 reporting cycle, the year 2055 was included as a mandatory reporting year for the first time. While all Member States submitted data for the other mandatory years 2025-2050, the completeness of reporting for 2055 varied across Member States.

Considering Total without LULUCF (Total GHGs, WEM), out of the 25 Member States (Belgium and Romania did not submit projections data during the 2025 QA/QC procedure), 12 (48%) Member States reported numeric values for the year 2055, while 13 (452%) Member States reported notation keys and required gap-filling by the ETC CM to ensure a complete time series until 2055 in view of the elaboration of the EU27 dataset. In these instances, the ETC CM extrapolated to 2055 by applying the 2050 values as constant values for the period 2051-2055. Figure 3.3 and Table 3.3 provide an overview of the reporting of 2055 during the 2025 cycle, and a split by Member State who reported this information.

Figure 3.3 Completeness of reporting of mandatory year 2055

Table 3.3 Overview by Member State of reported mandatory year 2055

Member State	2055	Member State	2055	Member State	2055
AT	No	ES	Yes	LV	No
BE	N/A	FI	Yes	MT	No
BG	Yes	FR	No	NL	Yes
CY	No	HR	No	PL	No
CZ	Yes	HU	No	PT	No
DE	No	IE	Yes	RO	N/A
DK	Yes	IT	Yes	SE	Yes
EE	Yes	LT	Yes	SI	No
EL	No	LU	No	SK	Yes

3.3 Addition of two new LULUCF sub-categories in (table 1a)

In the 2025 reporting cycle, two new sub-categories were introduced under category 4 (LULUCF) in Table 1a:

- 4.I Atmospheric deposition
- 4.J Nitrogen leaching and run-off

These additions were made to align the reporting framework with Article 2(2)(i) and (j) of the LULUCF Regulation, which requires Member States to account for emissions and removals from these processes within the land-use sector. Their inclusion enhances the consistency and comprehensiveness of LULUCF reporting under the Governance Regulation.

Although the inclusion of these new sub-categories was mandatory in the updated reporting template, reporting coverage remains very limited in this first implementation cycle.

Only Spain and Sweden reported numeric values for these new sub-categories, while all other Member States reported NAs, zeros, or blanks. Spain provided a complete time series from 2023 to 2055 for N₂O and total GHGs under the WEM scenario for category 4.J, and data from 2023 to 2030 for N₂O and total GHGs under the WAM scenario for category 4.J. Sweden reported data for N₂O and total GHGs under both the WEM and WAM scenarios for both categories 4.I and 4.J, however, only limited to the reference year 2023.

These two countries serve as examples of early and comprehensive adaptation to the new reporting categories, particularly Spain, which submitted a consistent and complete time series for the mandatory WEM scenario.

Overall, the countries that reported data for these new categories demonstrate early adaptation to the expanded LULUCF framework, laying the groundwork for broader adoption and improved methodological harmonisation in subsequent reporting cycles.

4 Summary of QA/QC results for Iceland, Norway, and Switzerland

Iceland, Norway and Switzerland are members of the EEA network and as such share some environmental commitments with the EU, such as for GHG emission reduction targets and mechanisms. Iceland and Norway take part in the EU ETS, while the Swiss Emission Trading System is linked to the EU ETS since 2020. In addition, Iceland and Norway have national targets under the ES Regulation (EU 2018/842). For these reasons, these countries can voluntarily participate in the QA/QC procedure of the EEA and the ETC CM. Table 4.1 displays an overview of the 2025 QA/QC results for Iceland, Norway and Switzerland.

Table 4.1 Overview of QA/QC results for Iceland, Norway, and Switzerland

Country	Iceland	Norway	Switzerland
First submission	17/03/2025	17/03/2025	15/03/2025
Resubmission	02/05/2025	NA	NA
Base Year	2023	2022	2022
Time series	2023-2055	2022-2040 (WEM) 2022-2035 (WAM)	2022-2040
Scenarios	WEM WAM	WEM WAM	WEM WAM WOM
Gases	All gases	All gases	All gases except ETS and ESR
Main sectors reported	Yes	Yes	No - Only sector totals
Report	Yes	Yes	No
Parameters	Yes	Yes	Yes
Model factsheet	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sensitivity Scenarios	Yes	Yes	Yes

As displayed in Figure 4.1 below, during the 2025 cycle, the ETC CM experts raised 20 questions to Iceland, 22 questions to Switzerland, and 21 questions to Norway respectively, amounting to 63 questions in total. This represented an increase compared to the 43 questions raised in 2023 (8 to Iceland, 20 to Norway and 15 to Switzerland).

Figure 4.1 Number of questions raised to Norway, Iceland and Switzerland

Figure 4.2 displays the distribution of questions by check for Norway, Iceland and Switzerland in the 2025 cycle. As for EU Member States, the completeness check is the one that raised most questions (36 questions or 57%).

Figure 4.2 Number of questions by check

Figure 4.3 illustrates the distribution of questions raised to Switzerland, Iceland and Norway by the ETC CM across categories in the 2025 reporting cycle. The largest share of question concerned multiple or all sectors (52.4%) or were more general questions related to the submission that did not pertain to a specific sector (“N/A”, 30.2%). Sector-specific question shares amounted to 1.6%, 1.6%, 0%, 7.9%, and 1.6% for “1. Energy”, “2. Industrial processes”, “3. Agriculture”, “4. LULUCF”, and “5. Waste”, respectively.

Figure 4.3 Distribution of questions across sectors

5 Conclusions and outlook for 2026

The results of the QA/QC procedure for the 2025 mandatory reporting cycle confirms that the process remains a cornerstone of the Union system for GHG projections. It continues to play a critical role in identifying reporting inconsistencies, supporting transparency, and strengthening Member States' national systems for projections. Building on the experience of previous cycles, the 2025 process benefited from a mature workflow and strong coordination between the ETC CM, the EEA, and Member States, ensuring an efficient review despite the growing complexity of reporting templates and new elements introduced under the Governance Regulation.

As in previous years, timeliness of submissions remains one of the key challenges. The official reporting deadline of 15 March 2025 was met by 12 Member States, while another seven submitted within six weeks of the deadline. The last submission was received in early June 2025, slightly later than in 2023. Moreover, 18 Member States resubmitted at least once, with some providing up to three resubmissions. The average time between the first and final submissions increased to approximately 81 days (compared to 54 days in 2023), with the last resubmission being received as late as 27 August 2025. Late submissions and resubmissions continue to create bottlenecks for the ETC CM and other EEA dataflow tasks, underlining the need for earlier submissions and enhanced national coordination. In consequence, this poses challenges for the timely analysis and processing of EU projections data. Moreover, late datasets hinder effective assessments and progress monitoring conducted by the EEA and the European Commission.

Completeness of mandatory reporting remained strong across the 25 reporting Member States. All submitted the required WEM scenario with full sector and gas coverage, as well as detailed LULUCF projections. The completeness of voluntary information improved slightly compared to 2023, with 21 Member States providing WAM projections and five reporting WOM scenarios. Improvements were also noted in the submission of parameters, showing greater engagement with optional reporting elements and an expanding use of the reporting templates. However, Belgium and Romania did not provide data during the 2025 QA/QC procedure, and their projections had to be gap-filled by the ETC CM.

The time series consistency and reference year checks confirmed overall alignment between historical and projected data. Most Member States selected either 2022 or 2023 as their reference year, reflecting reliance on recent inventory submissions. The ETC CM conducted targeted consistency checks to ensure smooth transitions between historical and projected series, avoiding artificial jumps or discontinuities. Twelve Member States required gap-filling of intermediate years between the reference year and 2050. When considering the complete time series up to 2055, all Member States except five required gap-filling of intermediate years. Specific challenges were addressed through case-by-case adjustments, ensuring a coherent EU-wide time series.

Regarding consistency and comparability, units and structure were generally consistent, though minor issues persisted in a few cases. Unit consistency slightly deteriorated compared with 2023 but was resolved during QA/QC through clarifications or resubmissions. For 18 Member States, higher WAM than WEM projections were detected, contrary to the expected scenario hierarchy. These cases were discussed and resolved through clarifications, with recommendations for Member States to document the rationale in their technical reports.

The accuracy and transparency checks yielded eight cases of sum inconsistencies, largely due to manual errors, and 25 questions relating to trends and outliers. These were generally explained by model updates or revised assumptions rather than errors. Twenty-one recalculation questions were also raised, primarily linked to updated methodologies or input data. None required corrective actions from the ETC CM. Overall, the QA/QC process continued to show a high degree of responsiveness and collaboration, with nearly all findings resolved through direct communication.

The reporting of parameters increased markedly in 2025, with all Member States except Belgium and Romania providing data. Commonly reported parameters included population, GDP, and EU ETS price, while others reflected national modelling specificities, such as fuel prices, nitrogen input, or technology costs. The Netherlands remained the only Member State to report parameters explicitly distinguishing CO₂ capture from biogenic and fossil sources. Despite growing diversity in parameter use, the ETC CM continued focusing checks on core recommended parameters to enhance consistency across submissions.

The 2025 reporting cycle also introduced new reporting elements that expand the analytical scope of GHG projections. These included:

- The mandatory reporting in table 3 on the differentiation of total CO₂ captured between biogenic CO₂ capture and fossil fuel-based CO₂ capture;
- The inclusion of the 2055 projection year, which enhances long-term assessment and alignment with climate neutrality goals; and
- Two new LULUCF sub-categories in Table 1a — *4.I Atmospheric deposition* and *4.J Nitrogen leaching and run-off* — aligned with the LULUCF Regulation.

Reporting coverage for these new elements varied. By the end of the QA/QC cycle, three Member States had distinguished biogenic CO₂ capture from fossil-based CO₂ capture in Table 3. Thirteen Member States (52%) reported numeric values for the year 2055, while twelve (48%) reported notation keys, requiring gap-filling by the ETC CM to ensure a complete time series until 2055 in view of the elaboration of the EU27 dataset. Additionally, Spain and Sweden were the only Member States that provided quantified data for both new LULUCF categories while most others reported notation keys or left the fields blank.

Overall, the 2025 QA/QC cycle demonstrated continued improvement in the quality, completeness, and transparency of Member States' projections. However, persistent issues such as late submissions, missing WAM scenarios, and limited reporting on new elements highlight the need for further guidance and capacity-building. Looking ahead, strengthening national coordination mechanisms and refining QA/QC tools – particularly for CO₂ capture, BECCS, and LULUCF – will be crucial to ensure consistency and readiness for the next reporting cycles.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use
AT	Austria
BE	Belgium
BECCS	Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage
BG	Bulgaria
CY	Cyprus
CZ	Czechia
DE	Germany
DG CLIMA	Directorate-General for Climate Action (at the European Commission)
DK	Denmark
EC	European Commission
EE	Estonia
EEA	European Environment Agency
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EL	Greece
ES	Spain
ESR	Effort Sharing Regulation
ETC CM	European Topic Centre on Climate change Mitigation
ETS	Emission Trading Scheme
EU	European Union
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System
EUR	Euro
FI	Finland
FR	France
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
Gov. Reg.	Governance Regulation (standing for the Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action Regulation (EU) 2018/1999)
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
IE	Ireland
IEA	International Energy Agency
IT	Italy
LT	Lithuania
LU	Luxemburg
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
LV	Latvia
MMR	Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (EU) No 525/2013
MT	Malta
NA, NE, NO, IE (or NK)	Not applicable, Not estimated, Not occurring, Included Elsewhere (Notation keys according to 2006 IPCC Guidelines)
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NL	Netherlands
PaMs	Policies and measures

Abbreviation	Name
PL	Poland
PT	Portugal
QA/QC	Quality assurance and quality control
RO	Romania
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
SK	Slovakia
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WAM	With additional measures
WEM	With existing measures
WOM	Without measures

Annex 1: Overview of corrections and gap-fillings applied by the ETC CM in 2025 cycle

MS	Error correction or gap filling	Gap filling of WAM with WEM	Sums gap filling (sectoral/national totals not reported)	Interpolation of intermediate years	Extrapolation to 2055	Other – specify/Comment
Austria	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	The blanks reported by EE for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Belgium	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	NA
Bulgaria	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	NA
Croatia	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	The blanks and zeros reported by HR for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. For IB.Navigation, the dataset was gap-filled by using the value of the latest historical inventory year for the entire time-series, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Cyprus	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	The zeros and blanks reported by CY for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. The values reported for CO2 emissions under category 5.A. are considered under category 5.C in both the WEM and WAM scenarios.
Czechia	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	The zeros and blanks reported by CZ for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. For CO2biomass, IB. Aviation, and International bunkers, the dataset was gap-filled by using the value of the latest historical inventory year for the entire time-series, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Denmark	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	The zeros and blanks reported by DK for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Estonia	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	The zeros and blanks reported by EE for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.

MS	Error correction or gap filling	Gap filling of WAM with WEM	Sums gap filling (sectoral/national totals not reported)	Interpolation of intermediate years	Extrapolation to 2055	Other – specify/Comment
Finland	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	The blanks reported by FI for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. The dataset was gap-filled by using the value of the latest historical inventory year for the entire time-series for MIB Aviation and MIB navigation, as required to compile complete Union projections.
France	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	The WAM scenario was gap filled for 2031-2055 by calculating the emissions of all gases and categories by applying the same interannual growth of the WEM by category and gas. For MIB Aviation and MIB navigation in the WAM scenario, the dataset was gap-filled by using the values of the WEM scenario, as required to compile complete Union projections. The zeros and blanks reported by FR for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. The dataset was gap-filled using the value of the latest historical inventory year for the entire time-series for CO2biomass.
Germany	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	NA
Greece	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	The zeros reported by EL for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. For CO2biomass, the value of the latest historical inventory year was used for the entire time-series for CO2biomass, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Hungary	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	The zeros and blanks reported by HU for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. The value of the latest historical inventory year for several categories was used for the entire time-series, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Ireland	Yes	No	No	No	No	The zeros reported by IE for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. For category 1B2, the dataset in the WAM scenario was gap filled for 2051-2054 using the values provided by IE during the communication.
Italy	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	The zeros reported by IT for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA

MS	Error correction or gap filling	Gap filling of WAM with WEM	Sums gap filling (sectoral/national totals not reported)	Interpolation of intermediate years	Extrapolation to 2055	Other – specify/Comment
						reports. For CO2biomass, in the WEM scenario, the value of the latest historical inventory year for the entire time-series was used, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Latvia	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	The zeros and blanks reported by LV for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Lithuania	No	No	No	No	No	NA
Luxembourg	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	The dataset was gap-filled for CO2 emissions from biomass, IB.Navigation, and International bunkers by using the value of the latest inventory value for the entire time-series, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Malta	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Mandatory years 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050, and 2055 in the WEM and WAM scenarios for all sectors and for some categories also mandatory years 2025 and 2030 were gap filled using the latest reported years when there are gaps (i.e. 2030 or 2040) up to 2055 just to complete the dataset. For the elaboration of the EU-27 projections, the time series was adjusted for several categories to ensure consistency by maintaining the reported emissions for all the time series (for both the RY and projections). The zeros and blanks reported by MT for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Netherlands	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	The dataset was gap-filled for years 2040-2055, for the WEM scenario, the emissions disaggregated categories were gap filled using the relative contribution of the latest available year; and for the WAM, the emissions of all gases and categories (not reported), have been calculated by applying the same interannual growth of the WEM by category and gas. The blanks reported by NL for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. For several categories, the value of the latest historical inventory year was used for the entire time-series, as required to compile complete Union projections.

MS	Error correction or gap filling	Gap filling of WAM with WEM	Sums gap filling (sectoral/national totals not reported)	Interpolation of intermediate years	Extrapolation to 2055	Other – specify/Comment
Poland	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	The zeros reported by PL for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Portugal	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	The zeros and blanks reported by PT for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. The dataset was gap-filled using the value of the latest historical inventory year for the entire time-series for MIB Aviation and MIB navigation, as required to compile complete Union projections.
Romania	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	NA
Slovakia	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	The zeros reported by SK for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Slovenia	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	For the elaboration of the EU-27 projections, the time series was adjusted for several categories to ensure consistency either by removing emissions or notation keys or by maintaining the reported emissions for all the time series (for both the RY and projections). The zeros and blanks reported by SI for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.
Spain	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	The zeros reported by ES for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports. The WAM dataset was gap-filled for years 2031-2055 by applying the same interannual growth of the WEM by category and gas.
Sweden	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	For the elaboration of the EU-27 projections, the time series was adjusted for 4I and 4J to ensure consistency by the reported emissions for the RY. The zeros reported by SE for several categories were treated as NK for the preparation of the EU-27 dataset used in the ETC CM and EEA reports.

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